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**LABORATORY OF PHYSICS
FOR MATERIALS AND
EMERGENT TECHNOLOGIES**

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QUANTUM MATERIALS AND TECHNOLOGIES
ADVANCED MATERIALS AND PROCESSES FOR ENERGY
ADVANCED MATERIALS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT
NEW PRINCIPLES AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR SENSING

TAILORED LIPID NANOSYSTEMS FOR TARGETED DELIVERY OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS AS A STRATEGY AGAINST SKIN AGING

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Skin aging, driven by intrinsic (chronological) and extrinsic (photoaging) factors, manifests through structural and functional deterioration, including wrinkles, dryness, and pigmentation irregularities. A shared molecular trigger in both processes is the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which promote oxidative damage and accelerate skin degeneration. A potent natural antioxidant (bioactive) was used as it shows promise as an anti-aging agent but faces limitations such as instability under UV exposure and restricted dermal penetration. This work presents the development of advanced lipid nanosystems for bioactive encapsulation and targeted delivery to aging skin. Two phospholipid-based formulations were engineered to optimize stability, entrapment efficiency, and biocompatibility. To enhance bioactive compounds action, lipid nanosystems were functionalized with the active targeting ligand A directed to receptors overexpressed in senescent cells, and an active targeting ligand B which promotes keratinocyte differentiation and barrier repair. Physicochemical characterization revealed nanoscale hydrodynamic diameters (113–150 nm), adequate zeta potentials (–6 to +20 mV), and high encapsulation efficiencies (>64%). All formulations demonstrated physical stability over three weeks and were successfully incorporated into a pseudoplastic semi-solid base suitable for topical application containing both liposomal formulations.

This integrated formulation approach, combining antioxidant delivery, biological targeting, and dermal compatibility, holds strong potential as a novel strategy for mitigating both chronological and photoinduced skin aging.